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Word Formation Process in Cricket Terminology: A Morphological Analysis

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Abstract

Since the game of cricket is popular in many countries with an enormous population, it does have a rich and ever-increasing vocabulary. Being popular among people with diverse languages, the game uses cross-linguistically significant vocabulary. Multilingual Neologisms are driven by the common use of language which was developed through cricket jargon. This paper observes selected cricket terminologies frequently used in the game of Cricket and analyzes the morphological process involved in them. First, the scope of and approaches to word-formation research will briefly be discussed. The researchers observe secondary resources from sports magazines and sports articles to collect sample jargon of Cricket. Then, the theoretical framework will be based on the approaches and strategies involved in word formation. Overall, 117 cricket jargon are categorized into 10 types and discussed in their forming process.

Keywords: Word Formation, Morphology, Cricket, Vocabulary

Introduction:

In the era of modern broadcasting and immense fandom for sports all over the world, cricket made its own space at the top of the list of all-time favorite sports of people. Though cricket was invented in the southeastern region of England during the Middle Ages, it has gained popularity since then. Especially, in the countries formerly colonized by the British Empire the game became the most popular sport. In 1844, the first international match was played between the USA and the British Empire's Canadian Province. And after that, in 1859 the English cricket team made its first international tour of the sport. By the middle of the 19th century, cricket became a well-established sport in the region of Australia, the Caribbean Islands, and British India. The famous *Ashes* series was first introduced in 1882 between England and Australia which reflects the historical rivalry and the mark of dominance of the two teams over the game (Brown, 1988). Cricket has been seen as an international sport ever since and every year thousands of matches are played between clubs and countries at both national and international levels. The recently finished ICC Cricket World Cup 2023 in India which was won by Australia bears the mark of cricket's being probably the 2nd most popular game around the world after football.

As McLuhan (1964) said, we are now living inside a *global village* which is dominated by technologies, viewers of cricket cannot be narrowed down to any particular country or region. And thus, the subject of language and linguistic theories found its way into cricket. Multilingual aspects and the formation of neologisms of the game are the topic of analysis in this paper. As cricket has the history and background from many regions of the world, and the jargon that the players, viewers, coaches, officials, and every person associated with the game uses every day, it is possible to morphologically analyze the constantly increasing cricket vocabulary. The etymology of words also helps us find the roots and their historical background may be useful to analyze the word structure. The authors of this paper also closely observe the multilingual nature of cricket terminologies reflected in their word formation. This way, the paper analyzes selected cricket vocabulary in the cross-linguistic morphological spectrum.

Objectives of the Study:

The objective of this research is to investigate selected cricket jargon etymologically focusing on the root of the words and the creation of certain vocabularies in this age-old sophisticated game. Interestingly, the cricket terminologies have a long history of formation in themselves which include colonialism, rapid mercantilism, globalization, and so on. Consequently, the game endorses a multilingual perspective in its ever-increasing vocabulary. The study reflects on the historical and linguistic aspects of certain terminologies used frequently in cricket in order to discover their morphological foundation. More precisely, the study posits selected jargon in different processes of word formation such as compounding, clipping, blending, borrowing, coinage, etc. Overall, the study creates a morphological corpus which may pave the way for those terminologies to be observed academically.

Literature Review:

If noticed carefully, it can be observed that many of the words in various languages are comparatively new or did not even exist a few decades earlier. If we look around, in both Bengali and English languages, some of the words formed in recent times and made a permanent place in the vocabulary of everyday spoken communication. For example, *Napa* is the brand name for paracetamol, manufactured by Beximco. But through the process of word formation, it became an independent morpheme (noun) for every kind of fever medication. Thus, the concept of neologism can be associated with the mentioned linguistic incident. Neologism is the acceptance of a word with a different contextual meaning than its existing meaning or a newly invented word having an independent meaning. In a recent study, it was found that neologism appears in a particular language in three steps principally. They are – borrowing, word forming, and derivation (Krishnamurthy, 2010). However, jargon in any given field of subject or area has already been introduced into the language of its users, such as in this case the sporting world of cricket. Cricket jargon has made their way into the glossary through different word formation processes.

This research has an association with some previous studies of a similar nature. The first such research is titled “Morphological Analysis of Word Formation Found in VOA News Articles” where Adha and Dania (2020) categorized 119 data from different VOA news articles into different types of word formation processes such as Derivation, Compound, Acronym, Initialism, Clipping, Abbreviation, and Conversion. They identified that the words changed semantically as well as in their parts of speech due to this way of formation. Their research matches the current article in the sense that both of them analyzed medium-specific terminologies using the word formation process.

While our research focuses on Cricket terms, Adha and Dania use VOA News articles related to education, science and technology, and health as their source of words.

Another research carried out by Indrian (2022) titled “A Morphological Analysis of Word Formation Process Used in Mobile Application Names” analyzes selected mobile applications from Google Play store and the result suggests that the word formation processes grouped in multiple processes, derivation, blending, and compounding. The principal purpose of Indrian’s article is to identify the processes of word formation reflected in the application names. Our study also opts to make a morphological investigation on a corpus of selected cricket terminologies. Before analyzing the cricket terms, the word formation processes involved are briefly discussed.

Morphology

According to Yule (2010), Morphology is “the study of words” (p.67). Generally, Morphology is the study where words and their structures are studied. Morpheme is the smallest unit of words which actually combines various processes to form a word with a comprehensible meaning. Though it does not analyze the meaning of words, through morphology the root meaning of words can be found. Thus, words and other word-like elements vary from language to language. For example, in Bangla a single form or word *Ashchhi* conveys in English like a full sentence, *I am leaving*. Morphologically, this sentence has 4 elements: I + am + leave + ing. These elements are called morphemes, which are the core components of word formation. There are various types of processes for forming a new word. Sometimes two or more words are connected together, sometimes words are clipped and even merged, or picked up from another language or simply named after someone or something. The common word formation processes are discussed below.

Compounding

When two separate forms combine to form a single new word with an independent meaning, this process is called compounding. Compounding appears in almost every language in the world. One good English example is the word ‘bookshelf’. Here, two independent words (book and shelf) are joined together to form a new word. The new word ‘bookshelf’ means a furniture where books are kept. So, undoubtedly, it has a different meaning from its parent words, book and shelf.

Rhyming Compound

Rhyming compound is similar to compounding of word formation. However, the primary difference between the two processes is that rhyming compounds rhyme in a certain manner. Rhyming compounds can be of two types. Some of them possess nonsensical constituents which are not semantically proven if used independently such as fuzzy-wuzzy, handy-dandy, etc. Here, the first word is followed by a suffix and then a nonsensical rhyming word is added. Another type is where the lexemes are based on meaningful units even when separately such as Cookbook, Primetime, Backpack, etc. It can be seen that the words have individual meanings, e.g., back and pack (Benczes, 2012).

Blending

As the name suggests, blending is where two separate forms are combined or blended to create a new form. A popular example of blending is *Smog*. Smog is the blended form of two separate words smoke and fog. The most significant difference between blending and compounding is that in blending the root words can be seen separately in the newly formed word, such as Wheelchair;

here wheel and chair are seen in the word. But in blended words such as *Brunch* (which is breakfast and lunch), the constituents are inseparable in the final product.

Clipping

This type of word formation generally means to reduce a word. This occurs when a word of multiple syllables shortens to produce new forms. For example, cab from cabriolets.

Eponym

The history of eponyms dates back to ancient times as it relates to the naming of things, which can be any type of things, objects, places, eras, theories, and even diseases. This morphological phenomenon is rather simple in manner and largely depends on behavioral patterns and sociological aspects. For instance, the galaxy Orion is believed to be named after God Orion, and Parkinson's disease is named after the scientist who discovered the symptoms first. Thus, any kind of proper noun can be transformed into an adjective when its semantic value changes.

Borrowing

Borrowing is one of the most common word formation processes in any language that has been exposed internationally. For example, both Bengali and English have many common vocabularies which have been derived from Persian (e.g. Pilaf/Pulao) etc.

Hypocorism

In Australian English hypocorism is widely used. It generally refers to the morphological process where a monosyllabic standard lexis is transformed by adding a suffix (e.g. -ly, -o, -ie, -y, etc.) to proclaim endearment or intimacy. Generally, hypocorism forms new words without changing the root meaning of the main word. For instance, big school bag is 'baggie', biscuit is 'bikkie', Isabelle is 'Izzy' etc.

Derivation

When free morphemes are connected with inflections, derivation occurs. Generally, these inflections do not convey separate meanings, but they modify or add meanings to the morphemes they are attached to. They are called suffixes and prefixes. For example, pre-, un-, dis-, ment-, -sion, -ly, -ing, etc. New words and terminologies often rely on derivation to achieve their meanings. For example, suffixes are added after a word, Google(n) to *Googling*; meaning searching for something on the internet using Google. Another example is *Preschool(n)*, where the prefix *pre-* is added before *school* to give it another meaning, which is the schooling of children before the actual school begins. Sometimes, both suffixes and prefixes can be added to form a new word. For instance, undoubtedly(adv) has three affixes. They are *un-*, *-ed*, and *-ly*.

Echoism

This is a process of word formation where the word's meaning conveys its sound. This is often called onomatopoeia in literature. In this formation process the lexicon imitates the sound which it means. It can be either natural or artificial. Such as, 'hiss' delivers the meaning of the sound of a snake and click means the sound of a lock.

Acronym

This is a process which takes the first letters or the first two or three letters of a word or phrase and then puts them together to form a new word. There are two types of acronyms, they are: Alphabetism, where the initial letters or alphabets are taken to form a new word (Yule, 2010). For example, ATM (automated teller machine). This type of formation is also called initialism. Another type is, where the shortened forms are pronounced as single words, such as, NATO, UNESCO, etc. Acronyms sometimes play an interesting role in creating a semantic value as well. For instance, some organizations formed their acronyms in such a way that represent their value or motto. In the *Harry Potter* series by JK Rowling, the author introduced an acronym “OWL” which means Ordinary Wizarding Level. This also metaphorically represents the owl’s significance in the book.

Methodology

Data Collection

This research bears a qualitative approach. The authors used secondary data sources such as ESPNcricinfo.com, The Daily Star, YouTube, and live cricket commentary. The terminologies are gathered through close observation and studying relevant documents (web and print articles, online interviews, etc.) related to sports.

Data Analyzing Technique

The authors followed the five phases of data analysis and their interaction. Firstly, the data was compiled through the mentioned sources. Secondly, the collected data are sorted into fragments to disassemble. By this procedure, the authors filtered out the frequently used jargon of cricket to analyze the word formation process they have fallen into. Thirdly, the collected data or the selected jargon is categorized into word formation processes such as borrowing, blending, clipping, acronyms, neologism, coinage, and multiple processes. Finally, the authors reassembled and interpreted the data to explain the morphological background of the cricket jargon.

Findings and Discussion

After categorizing the data, the researchers found some process of word formation, in which the data can be seen in the following table. We find 117 data from jargon used in cricket. By categorizing them morphologically, there are mainly 10 types of words.

No.	Type of word formation	Number of data
1.	Compounding	47
2.	Rhyming Compound	7
3.	Blending	4
4	Clipping	2
5	Borrowing	3

6	Eponym	6
7	Hypocorism	16
8	Echoism	6
9	Affixation	11
10	Acronym	15

Compounding in Cricket Terminology

The researchers found 47 data classified into compounding. The following table shows the summary of the data:

Table 02: Cricket jargon with compounding		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Compounding Process
1	All-rounder	All(adv) + Round(adj) + er
2	Bodyline	Body(n) + Line (n)
3	Batsman	Bat(n)+s+ Man(n)
4	Ball-tampering	Ball(n)+Tampering(v)
5	Bat-pad	Bat(n)+Pad(n)
6	Blackcaps	Black(adj)+Cap(n)
7	Bowl-out	Bowl(n)+Out(preposition)
8	Chest-on	Chest(n) + On(preposition)
9	Cross-bat	Cross(v) + Bat(n)
10	Dead-ball	Dead (adj)+Ball(n)
11	Flat-track	Flat(adj) + Track(n)
12	Full-toss	Full(adj) + Toss(v)
13	Half-volley	Half(adj)+Volley(n)
14	Hat-trick	Hat(n)+Trick(n)

15	Hawk-Eye	Hawk(n)+Eye(n)
16	Inside-out	In(preposition)+Side(noun)+Out(preposition)
17	Knuckle-ball	Knuckle(n)+Ball(n)
18	Longhop	Long(adj)+ Hop (n)
19	Leg-break	Leg (n)+Break(verb)
20.	Longhop	Long(adj)+Hop(n)
21	Match-fixing	Match(n)+Fix(v)+ing (inflection)
22	Minefield	Mine(n)+Field(n)
23	Monkeygate	Monkey(n)+Gate(n)
24	Nightwatchman	Night(n)+Watch(v)+Man(n)
25	No-ball	No(adv)+Ball(n)
26	Off-break	Off(preposition)+Break(v)
27	Out-swing	Out(preposition)+Swing(v)
28	Overarm	Over(adv)+Arm(n)
29.	Overrate	Over(adv)+Rate(n)
30.	Pinch-hitter	Pinch(n)+Hitter(n)
31	Run-chase	Run(n)+Chase(v)
32	Sandpapergate	Sand(n)+Paper(n)+Gate(n)
33	Sight-screen	Sight(n)+Screen(n)
43	Stonewall	Stone(n)+Wall(n)
44	Switch-hit	Switch(n)+Hit(v)
45	Whitewash	White(n)+Wash(v)
46	Toe-crusher	Toe(n)+Crusher(n)
47	Wicketkeeper	Wicket(n)+Keep(v)+er

All-rounder

An 'all(adv)-rounder(n)' is a player who has expertise in both batting and bowling. This is a special kind of player who can contribute to the game with both their abilities. Depending upon their ability they might also be called a 'batting all-rounder' or a 'bowling all-rounder'. These days the term is often used more specifically as 'pace-bowling allrounder' or 'spin-bowling' allrounder. In morphological analysis, this is a hyphenated compound word: all(adj) + round (adj) + er (suffix).

Batsman

This indicates a player who can perform well with the bat rather than bowl. Though anybody who comes to face the bowlers with the bat can be called a batsman, not everybody has the same expertise. The word has three morphemes:

bat(n) + s + man(n) = open class free morpheme + inflectional bound morpheme + open class free morpheme

One might say that since the tool in cricket is 'bat', why is it not called 'batman' instead of 'batsman'? But since the word 'bat' also indicates an animal, using it without inflection creates another compounding which is the comic book superstar 'Batman'. To avoid confusion and make a distinction, deliberately the inflectional 's' is used after 'bat', and it becomes a unique cricket word. To avoid sexism, in modern days instead of 'batsman' many commentators use 'batters' which falls in a different category of word formation process.

Ball-tampering

This hyphenated compound refers to illegal tampering done by the fielding side on the surface of the ball while playing cricket. It has two open class free morphemes and a bound morpheme: ball (noun) + tamper (verb) + ing (suffix). This is used as a noun.

Faf du Plessis was found guilty of *ball-tampering* back in 2013. (noun)

Bat-pad

The word has two open class free morphemes creating a hyphenated compound: Bat (noun) + pad (noun) = Bat-pad. The meaning – the ball touching both the bat and pad of the batter while playing – created through this compounding is completely different from the two morphemes involved. However, there are three possible parts of speech frequently used in cricket with this compounding:

That's clearly a *bat-pad*. (noun)

Rohit Sharma has *bat-padded* the off-cutter. (verb)

It was a *bat-padded* shot. (adjective)

Blackcaps

Black (adjective) and caps (noun) are two free morphemes having different meanings. However, when they are attached and used as a compound, it refers to the New Zealand cricket team who are also known by this title. It is used as a noun.

Blackcaps are a proud cricketing nation. (noun)

Bodyline

Body(n) and line(n) are two free morphemes with independent meanings. In cricket, it indicates a type of fast bowling when the bowler bowls in a leg-stump line but pitches it short with pace to unsettle the batsman on the crease. In the language of word formation, the word is a non-hyphenated compound having two free morphemes which separately mean nothing that is connected to cricket whereas together it becomes a jargon of cricket. For example:

Sakib Al Hasan and Mashrafe bowled Australia to a series-levelling victory amid hopes that *Bodyline* was beaten. (noun)

Bowl-out

This word also includes two open class free morphemes creating a hyphenated compound: bowl (verb) + out (preposition). This indicates a former tiebreaker rule in limited-overs cricket where five bowlers used to get a chance to hit the unguarded wickets from each team much like the penalty shoot-out of football. Usually, the compound is used only as a noun:

The match between India and Pakistan in the 2007 World Cup was decided through a *bowl-out*. (noun)

Chest-on

This word is a combination of a free morpheme: Chest (noun) and a bound morpheme: on (preposition). The two morphemes have separate meanings but when they are combined, it becomes a cricket term indicating a bowler's bowling style which involves delivering the ball with his/her "chest facing the batsman" (Williamson, 2021). This compound has three possible parts of speech:

Andrew Flintoff's bowling action is *chest-on*. (noun)

Brett Lee bowls *chest-on*. (adverb)

Malinga has a *chest-on* slinging action. (adjective)

Cross-bat

In this word, there are two open class free morphemes: cross (verb) + bat (noun). Though there are two different parts of speech between the two morphemes, the compound 'Cross-bat' can be used in several forms of parts of speech:

Mushfiq played a great *cross-batted* shot. (adjective)

Buttler doesn't mind playing *cross-batt*. (noun)

Shanaka *cross-batted* very often in his short innings. (verb)

Deadball

In this compounded word, two open class morphemes: dead (adj) + ball (n) formed a new word 'Deadball' which indicates the call of the umpire when the batsman can score no runs, or they will not be given out. Additionally, if the ball bounces twice or more before reaching out to the batsman, the umpire may call that a deadball. Again, it is an example that has two free morphemes which create a cricket compound. It can be used in a sentence such as:

Malinga delivered a *deadball* while bowling against Bangladesh. (noun)

Flat-track or Shirtfront

The two compounds are used alternatively to refer to the pitches or tracks which do not help the bowlers much in terms of generating pace or spin making it comfortable for the batters to hit boundaries and over-boundaries. 'Flat(adj)-track(n)' is a hyphenated compound having two free morphemes whereas 'shirtfront' is a non-hyphenated compound having two free morphemes. Both compounds are mostly used as nouns.

India offers *flat-tracks* to encourage the audience. (noun)

Australia has almost no *shirtfronts*. (noun)

Full-toss

The compound is formed with two open class morphemes: full (adjective) and toss (verb) having independent meanings and parts of speech. However, in cricket, it means a bowling delivery when the bowl reaches straight to the batsman or beyond the position of the batsman without touching the ground. This compound is used as a noun:

Brett Lee bowled a fast *full-toss* to Graeme Smith. (noun)

Half-volley

Half-volley is an often-used compound in cricket to indicate a form of bowling when the bowler pitches the ball close enough for the batsman to strike after it makes one bounce on the ground. In this situation, a batsman barely has to move while hitting the ball. As it is understood from the definition, the compound 'half-volley' has no connection to the independent morphemes 'half (adjective)' and 'volley (noun)'. The compound is used in cricket as a noun only:

Ishant Sharma bowled a *half-volley* which was hit for a boundary. (noun)

Hat-trick

It means when a bowler is successful to get three batsmen out in three consecutive deliveries. This compound having two free morphemes, Hat(n) and Trick(n) is always used with a hyphen making it a special cricket vocabulary.

Wasim Akram is the only man having two *hattricks* in Tests and ODIs.

Hawk-Eye

This refers to a cricket technology used to enquire about a caught or leg before wicket dismissal of a batsman. This compound also has two free morphemes: Hawk(n) + Eye(n) which if used separately will have no connection with cricket. In a sentence, it can be used as a noun,

The umpire used *hawk-eye* to clear out the appeal of the bowler. (noun)

Inside-out

This hyphenated compound comprises three open class morphemes: in (preposition) + side (noun) + out (preposition). The morphemes have separate identities as single words but when they are added, it becomes a common cricket term which suggests a type of shot played by the batters when they usually play off-spin deliveries. This compound has two different parts of speech:

Ashraful moved *inside-out*. (adverb)

Aftab played a lofted *inside-out* shot. (adjective)

Knuckleball

It is a non-hyphenated compound having two free morphemes: Knuckle (noun) and ball (noun). In cricket, the compound refers to a type of slower delivery bowled by the fast bowlers using the knuckles of the bowling hand intending to deceive the batters. This form of bowling was invented by “South Africa-born all-rounder Kenny Jackson” (G, 2023). This is used as a noun.

Bhuvneshwar Kumar bowled a good *knuckleball*. (noun)

Leg-break, Leg-spin, Leg-cutter, Leg-bye, Leg-slip

There are a number of cricket compounds that start with the morpheme ‘leg (noun)’. ‘Leg-break’ and ‘leg-spin’ are used alternatively to indicate a spin bowling trajectory when the ball spins away from the right-handed batsman after bouncing on the ground. ‘Leg-cutter’ is a similar delivery but bowled by a pace bowler instead of a spin bowler. ‘Leg-bye’ refers to a run taken by a batter after hitting the ball not with the bat but with any part of the body except the wrist. ‘Leg-slip’ is a fielding position set behind the leg side of the batsman near the left side of the wicketkeeper for a right-handed batsman or to the right side of the wicketkeeper for a left-handed batsman. These hyphenated compounds have multiple uses of parts of speech:

Shane Warne is the best *leg-spin* bowler in history. (adjective)

Ravi Bishnoi bowls leg-spin (adverb).

Alok Kapali bowls *leg-break*. (adverb)

That's a great *leg-break* delivery. (adjective)

His *leg-spin* is deadlier than his top spin. (noun)

Miraz took a *leg-bye*. (noun)

Mustafiz bowls the best *leg-cutters*. (noun)

Dhoni called in for a *leg-slip*. (noun)

Longhop

Long(adj) and hop(n) have two independent meanings and free morphemes. But the two lexes are combined to create cricket jargon which indicates a bad delivery that falls too short on the ground probably because the bowler aimed for a bouncer which went wrong and became a very easy slow-paced delivery to hit a boundary. It can be used both as a noun and an adjective.

Sharma delivered a *longhop* before Hasan. (noun)

Ashraful's *longhop* bowling caused Bangladesh to lose the series against Australia. (adjective)

Match-fixing, Spot-fixing

These two compounds which end with the word 'fixing' are a combination of two-word formation processes. This is definitely a compound because they have two free morphemes: match + fix, and spot + fix. But since they end with the bound morpheme 'ing', the rule of affixation is also found. Match-fixing refers to the illegal practice of fixing the result of the game beforehand. Spot-fixing refers to unveiling any decision taken on the spot through any sign given to the bookies or following any order given by the bookies while being on the field. The compounds are used both as nouns and adjectives.

Salman Butt was involved in one of the most shameful *match-fixing* scandals. (adjective)

Mohammad Asif had done *spot-fixing* several times. (noun)

Minefield

This compound consists of two open class free morphemes which refers to the type of pitch cricketers get in a test match mostly on day 4 and day 5 when lots of cracks are opened on the ground helping especially the spinners. It is used as a noun.

The pitch has become a *minefield* after all the hustle and bustle of the first three days. (noun)

Monkeygate

‘Monkeygate’ indicates one of the biggest controversies involving two cricketers Andrew Symonds of Australia and Harbhajan Sing of India taken place “in 2008, where the off-spinner allegedly hurled a racist abuse at Symonds referring to him as a ‘Monkey’” (Suresh, 2020). It is understood from the information that there is no connection between the meanings of the two free morphemes: monkey (noun), gate (noun) and the compound itself. This non-hyphenated compound can be used both as a noun and an adjective.

One of the biggest controversies of the game is the *Monkeygate*. (noun)

The *Monkeygate* scandal went through a formal inquiry. (adjective)

Nightwatchman

Nightwatchman is a jargon used in cricket having three different parts of speech within the compound. Here ‘night’ is a noun, ‘watch’ is a verb and ‘man’ is a noun. These independent forms refer to a batsman who is sent to a comparatively advanced position in an extraordinary situation in the game. In this case, the batter who is promoted is not a specialist batter but can hold one end without giving up his/her wicket. Morphologically it is a very interesting word: night (noun) + watch (verb) + man (noun) = 3 open class free morphemes

No-ball

No-ball refers to the illegal deliveries bowled by the bowlers due to over-stepping or bowling an over-waist full-toss or touching the stumps on the non-striking end at the time of bowling. This compound has two free morphemes: no (adverb) and ball (noun). It is used only as a noun.

Makhaya Ntini unfortunately got a wicket on the *no-ball*. (noun)

Off-break, Off-spin, Off-side

There are some common cricket terms such as ‘off-break’, ‘off-spin’ and ‘off-side’ having two independent morphemes but meaning completely something new. ‘Off-break’ and ‘off-spin’ are used alternatively like ‘leg-break’ and ‘leg-spin’ mentioned above. The only difference is that in this type of bowling, the ball spins towards a right-hander and spins away from a left-hander. ‘Off-side’ indicates the side of the field which is close to the off-stump of the batter. All these are used as multiple parts of speech in sentences.

Harbhajan was an *off-spin* bowler. (adjective)

Shahid Afridi bowls *off-break* to the left-hander. (adverb)

Virat Kohli is strong on his *off-side*. (noun)

Out-swing, In-swing

There are lots of words connected to 'swing' in cricket. For this reason, compounds such as 'out-swing', 'in-swing' are very common in the game. 'Out-swing' refers to a bowling type with which a pacer or a spinner swings the ball away from the batsman. On the contrary, 'in-swing' refers to the bowling when bowlers swing the ball inside the zone of the stumps or body of the batsman. These types of compounds often have this formation: preposition + verb = verb/gerund adjective, in (preposition) + swing (verb) = inswing (verb)

Kulasekara *out-swings* the ball sharply. (verb)

That is an in-swinging yorker. (gerund adjective)

Overarm, Roundarm, Underarm

There are a few frequently used compounds in cricket which end with the free morpheme 'arm'. All these are bowling stances adopted by the bowlers. When a bowler's hand is above the shoulder, it is called overarm. When the bowler's arm is extended about 90 degrees from their body at the release time, it is called roundarm. Underarm refers to a bowling action when the bowl is bowled "with the hand below the elbow" (Mukherjee, 2016). In the sense of morphology, the words have two open class morphemes: Over (preposition - bound morpheme) + arm (noun - free morpheme) = Overarm (compound), Under (preposition - bound morpheme) + arm (noun - free morpheme) = Underarm (compound), Round (adjective - free morpheme) + arm (noun - free morpheme) = Roundarm (compound). The compounds can be used as multiple parts of speech:

Waqar had developed a modern day *roundarm* action. (adjective)

Shane Bond traditionally bowled *overarm*. (adverb)

Trevor Chappel *underarmed* to Brian McKechnie. (verb)

Over-rate

Over-rate indicates the average number of overs bowled per hour in an innings by the bowling team. The umpires calculate over-rate by dividing the number of overs by the number of hours of play in an innings to justify the pace of the game. This common cricket jargon is actually a hyphenated compound having two independent morphemes: over (preposition) + rate (noun). This is used both as a noun and an adjective.

The *overrate* rule was applied and the bowling team got punished. (adjective)

Pakistan was charged for slow *overrate*. (noun)

Pinch-hitter

This term refers to a batter who is often promoted up the order because of his/her hitting ability. This word too is a hyphenated compound having two open class morphemes. The formation of the word is as follows: pinch (noun - free morpheme) + hit (verb - free morpheme) + er (suffix - bound morpheme). With the addition of the suffix, the compound also includes the rule of affixation.

Run-chase, Run-up

In cricket, when two batters on the crease complete one cycle of running from one end to the other end of the pitch, it is called a 'run'. In that sense, the word 'run' can be used both as a noun and a verb in cricket. When other morphemes are connected to the word 'run' they create separate compounds such as 'run-chase' – meaning the chase of the score by the team batting second in order to win the match and 'run-up' - meaning the running of the bowlers before they do the delivery. These compounds are used mostly as nouns.

Indians do well at the time of *run-chase*. (noun)

Pacers have a bigger *run-up* than the spinners. (noun)

Sandpapergate

This refers to the use of sandpaper on the surface of “the cricket ball to extract enhanced reverse swing” by the three Australian players: David Warner, Steven Smith and Cameron Bancroft (Tikka & Garg, 2018). This compound has three open class free morphemes - sand (noun), paper (noun), gate (noun) - all having different meanings. However, together they become the title of the infamous ball-tampering incident which has no connection with the meanings of the three morphemes. The compound is used both as a noun and an adjective.

The three players involved in the *Sandpapergate* scandal were punished. (adjective)

The *Sandpapergate* is the biggest scandal of recent times. (noun)

Sight-screen

This word is a formation of two independent lexicons which have a distinct meaning of their own. Sight(n) means ability to see and screen(n) means a flat panel or sheet but in cricket it holds a completely different meaning which refers to the blank screens placed on both sides of the bowler's end beyond the boundary line especially to help the batsman focus while facing the bowlers.

The bowler did not notice the *sight-screen* before bowling. (Noun)

Stonewall

This compound in cricket refers to the overdefensive playing style of a batsman which is very useful especially in test match cricket. Since their defense is very strong, they are called stonewalls. This nonhyphenated compound has two free morphemes having independent meanings. It is used as multiple parts of speech.

Pujara is India's new *stonewall*. (noun)

Pakistan adopted a new mode of *stonewall* tactics. (adjective)

Finn's duty was to *stonewall* one end of the wicket. (verb)

Switch-hit

‘Switch-hit’ means a modern cricket shot in cricket. In this case, the batsman suddenly “changes” the “grip after the ball is bowled” making “a right-hander [turn] into a left-hander and also the other way around” (Adhikari, n.d.). In the sense of morphology, the hyphenated compound comprises two free morphemes: switch (verb) and hit (verb). The compound is also used as a verb and occasionally as a noun.

Kevin Pietersen *switch-hits* Murali. (verb)

He suddenly played a *switch-hit*. (noun)

Toe-crusher

This word is a combination of compounding and affixation because here, two free morphemes: toe (noun), crush (verb) and a bound morpheme ‘er’ are included. This indicates a form of yorker delivery that is pitched right in the block-whole of the batsman giving almost no space to hit the ball. The compound is mostly used as a noun.

Waqar Younis was a champion of bowling *toe-crushers*. (noun)

Wicketkeeper

It refers to the player who keeps the wicket standing behind the stumps. In a morphological sense, this word is a non-hyphenated compound: wicket (noun) + keeper (noun). However, the presence of the suffix “er” at the end of the word “keeper”, also posits the word in the category called affixation.

Whitewash

This is a very common compound used in cricket to mean that a team has won all the games in a bilateral series. The compound consists of two free morphemes: white (adjective) and wash (verb). But together it becomes a term in cricket meaning completely something else. The word is used both as a noun and a verb.

England *whitewashed* Australia. (verb)

The series ended in a *whitewash*. (noun)

Rhyming Compounds

There are some unusual words formed on the basis of their sound specifically used in cricket. The researchers have found 7 such expressions classified into rhyming compounds.

Table 03: Cricket jargon with rhyming compound
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No.	Cricket Terminologies	Rhyming Compound Process
1	Dilly-dolly	d and l – sounds
2	Cow-corner	c and r -sounds
3	Dibbly-dobbly	d and l -sounds
4	Diamond-duck	d – sound
5	Power-play	p – sound
6	Wagon-wheel	w – sound
7	Run-rate	r – sound

Dilly-dolly

The word dilly(n) is an English slang word which means an exceptional person or event and on the other hand, dolly(n) simply means a doll where the inflectional suffix -y is added to imitate a childlike or adorable sound. In cricket, through the word formation process of rhyming compound these two words are combined to indicate the very easy catch which went missing because of the indecision of the fielder. The 'd' sound is used in both lexicons to create an alliterative effect.

Rubel missed a *dilly-dolly* catch. (adjective)

Cow-corner

It is a fielding position that is usually between mid-wicket and long-on where the fielding team does not expect the batters to hit. The exact position on the field depends upon a batsman's handedness (left or right). Nevertheless, there is no rule that a batsman cannot hit anywhere specifically, it is just an assumption of the fielding captain while s/he places the fielders. Also, it is used as slang for those fielders who are considered not that agile and placed by the captain in such a position. As can be seen, the word is a hyphenated compound noun but many use it as a phrase without giving the hyphen in the middle.

Dibbly-dobbly

It can be called an ideal rhyming compound because this word has no base. It is just a rhyming expression which later became a word. This process may also be called 'reduplication'. This word refers to gentle medium pacers who are considered not that threatening like the fast bowlers. In the 90s New Zealand had a pack of "slow-medium men" like Gavin Larsen, Chris Harris, and Rod Latham (Monga, 2009). This compound is used both as nouns and adjectives.

Where have all the *dibbly-dobblies* gone? (noun)

Aftab was a *dibbly-dobbly* pacer. (adjective)

Diamond-duck

This compound refers to a batsman's getting out without facing any legal delivery. This usually happens when a batsman gets run-out from the non-striking end. This is an ironic expression used to intend fun or to ridicule someone who got out this way. In the sense of morphology, it is a hyphenated rhyming compound having two free morphemes. This is used as a noun.

Soumya again gets a *diamond-duck*. (noun)

Powerplay

It indicates those few overs where the fielding captain is not allowed more than two fielders outside the 30-yard circle. This is practiced in the white ball cricket meaning the ODI and T-20 matches. In the language of word formation, this is a non-hyphenated compound noun having two free morphemes.

Run-rate

This refers to the rate of scoring per over in an innings for the batting team. The compound has a consonance with the repetition of the sound 'r' for which it becomes a rhyming compound. It is used as a noun.

The *run-rate* is getting higher. (noun)

Wagon-Wheel

It indicates "[a] circular graph or line-drawing depicting the region in which a batsman has scored his runs" (Williamson, 2021). This hyphenated compound consists of two open class free morphemes: wagon (noun) and wheel (noun). The 'w' sound rhymes in this word for which it is more suited as a rhyming compound.

Blending

The researchers found 4 data classified into Blending.

Table 04: Cricket jargon with Blending		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Blending
1	Banglawash	Bangla(desh)+Wash
2	Supersub	Super+Sub(stitute)
3	wrong'un	Wrong+One
4	Gazunder	Goes+Under

Banglawash

Bangladeshi cricket commentator Athar Ali Khan spontaneously coined this word “after Bangladesh whitewashed New Zealand at home in 2010” (“We have to be realistic,” 2015). This blended word has been added to the cricketing dictionary after that series and is being used as a Bangladeshi alternative to the word ‘whitewash’. The blending comes from the supposed phrase, ‘Bangladeshi Whitewash’ which becomes a popular colloquial term ‘Banglawash’ soon after the famous series win. Like, its alternative ‘whitewash’, ‘Banglawash’ is used both as a noun and a verb.

The 4-0 series win of Bangladesh over New Zealand was a *Banglawash*. (noun)

New Zealand has been *Banglawashed* twice so far. (verb)

Supersub

This word is a blended version of the two words: super and substitute. This refers to a substitute player who may come in place of any other player depending upon the situation of the game. This rule is no longer practiced in cricket. In the sense of morphology, this word also has a rhyming compound with the repetition of ‘s’ sound.

Vikram Solanki of England was the first *supersub* in the history of international cricket. (noun)

Wrong'un

The full form of the word is ‘wrong one’ but gradually this word is blended and became popular in this shortened form followed by its assimilating pronunciation. This is considered an artistic type of leg spin bowling when instead of going away from the right-hander it spins inside like an off-spin delivery of the right-armed.

Gazunder

This is another blending which comes from the use of assimilation in pronunciation. The full form of the word is – goes + under = Gazunder. It is a situation when the ball skids a little after being pitched and does not bounce as it normally should and eventually, the ball passes under the bat of the batsman to the hands of the wicketkeeper or hits the wicket.

Clipping

The researchers found 2 data classified into clipping.

Table 05: Cricket jargon with clipping		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Clipping

1	Bunsen	Bunsen←Bunsen Burner
2	Rip	Rip←Ripper

Bunsen

It is a term to describe the pitch of a cricket field that gives a clear advantage to the slow bowlers. When such a pitch is made by the home country where the game is being played, this word is often used as slang rather than for any good intention. The actual term is Bunsen Burner = Turner but often, commentators use the first part of the phrase as an alternative to the word ‘turner’.

Rip

This word is used to suggest the big turns of a spin bowler. When this happens, the batsman becomes so puzzled that, s/he misses the ball altogether. In this situation, the maximum amount of spin is exerted by the bowlers who are generally finger spinners. The actual word is ‘ripper’ which gets clipped and used as just ‘rip’.

Borrowing

The researchers found 3 data classified into Borrowing.

Table 06: Cricket jargon with Borrowing		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Borrowing
1	Doosra	Urdu
2	Teesra	Urdu
3	Jalebi	Urdu

Doosra

The most common example of borrowing is the word ‘doosra’. The word is both in Urdu and Hindi language. Since a former Pakistani Spin bowler, Saqlain Mushtaq, is given the credit for inventing the technique, it can be assumed that the term’s origin is in Urdu language (Dhariyal, 2023). It means ‘the second one’ or ‘the other one’ in English. This term was introduced in cricket in the late 90s by Mushtaq but later in the 2000s was more popularized by Sri Lanka cricket genius Muttiah Muralitharan whose deliveries were faster and almost unplayable. Nevertheless, this is one of the borrowings commonly uttered in cricket commentary due to the introduction of cricket in South Asia in the colonial era.

Teesra and Jalebi

The story behind this borrowing is similar to Doosra. It is another form of variation bowled by an off-spinner much like the orthodox back-spinner. This word means ‘the third one’ in English. This too is credited to the Pakistani spinner Saqlain Mushtaq. However, the same form of bowling is often humorously called ‘Jalebi’ because of its sharp and unplayable term. The word ‘Jalebi’ came after a popular subcontinental sweet snack. Both the words Teesra and Jalebi are available in Urdu and Hindi which are themselves very similar languages. But because the bowling form was invented by Mushtaq, it can be said that both words are borrowed from Urdu and became popular cricket jargon.

Eponyms

The researchers found 5 data classified into Eponym.

Table 08: Cricket jargon with Eponym		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Eponym
1	Kolpak	Maros Kolpak
2	Bazball	Brendon McCullum (Baz)
3	Dilscoop	Tilakratne Dilshan
4	Mankad	Vinoo Mankad
5	Chinaman	Chinese
6	Yorker	York (County of England)

Kolpak

This is a popular eponym in cricket which is coined after “Maros Kolpak, a Slovak Handball player” (“The Kolpak rule explained,” 2017). This man famously won a court appeal that permitted him to play in Germany as a representative of a country that has the European Union Association Agreement. Surprisingly, many cricketers around the world, especially from South Africa, have used this path to take a long-term deal in the county cricket of England and eventually, ‘Kolpak’ has become a very common cricket term.

Bazball

Andrew Miller, cricket author and one of the editors of ESPNcricinfo, coined the term ‘Bazball’ explaining it as an “ineffable mind-trick” while playing test cricket (Miller). The term is inspired by the spirited personality of Brendon McCullum, the head coach of England, whose nickname is ‘Baz’. This eponym word is used as a noun.

Bazball has become a cult style in cricket. (noun)

Dilscoop

This is one of the most famous examples of eponyms in cricket terminology. The full derivative is Dilshan + Scoop = Dilscoop. It refers to a shot called ‘paddle scoop’ which a Sri Lanka cricketer called Tilakratne Dilshan used to play so masterfully that the term ‘Dilscoop’ was coined honoring him in the 2009 ICC World T20 (Verma, 2016). This word is used as a noun.

Shakib plays the *Dilscoop* in a crunch situation. (noun)

Mankad

It is an infamous cricket term coined after a former India cricketer named Vinoo Mankad. This is “basically the act of a bowler running out a batter on the non-striker’s end if he/she is backing up and too far ahead of the crease before the ball was delivered” (Kataria, 2022). This term was introduced in cricket in the 1947-48 India tour of Australia when Mankad ran Billy Brown out in this way at Sydney cricket ground which was historically the first time “in international cricket” (Kataria, 2022). Since this word exactly coins the name of the man, it can be categorized as an eponym. This word is used as both nouns and verbs.

Ashwin thinks *Mankading* does not break the spirit of the game. (verbal noun)

Fazalhaq Farooqi has *mankaded* Shadab Khan. (verb)

Manhattan

It refers to a “bar graph of runs scored per over” in an innings (Williamson, 2021). This graph is named after the district of Manhattan in New York, USA. It is an ideal example of eponyms which are not named after a human being but after a place.

Chinaman

This compound consists of two free morphemes: China (noun) and man (noun). This refers to the left-arm spinner’s leg-spin or wrist-spin bowling. Former West Indian spinner Elis Achong who is known to be “the first Test cricketer of Chinese ancestry” is believed to have originated the unexpected bowling-style back in the 1930s (“Leggie in the mirror,” 2021”). Since no one understood this style back then, they simply started calling it ‘Chinaman’ to specify the style with Achong. In the sense of morphology, it is a non-hyphenated compound used both as a noun and an adjective.

Kuldip Yadav’s *Chinaman* is troublesome for most batters. (noun)

Tabraiz Shamsi is a promising *Chinaman* bowler. (adjective)

Yorker

This suggests a lethal bowling delivery when the bowler lands the ball directly at the batter’s feet and it becomes “extremely difficult to hit” (“The origins of cricket jargon,” n.d.). Another theory says that the word means to deceive or to cheat the batter. Following the first theory, the word is

undoubtedly an example of an eponym. Since there is a suffix ‘er’ in the word after the root word ‘York,’ it can also be put in the category of affixation.

Hypocorism

There are many words used as hypocorism in cricket. The commentators use these terms both in formal and informal discussions. The researchers found 16 data classified into Hypocorism.

Table 07: Cricket jargon with Hypocorism		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Hypocorism
1	Aussie	Australia
2	Bhajji	Harbhajan Singh
3	Gilly	Adam Gilchrist
4	Inzi	Inzamam-ul-Haq
5	Mahi	Mahendra Singh Dhoni
6	Yuvi	Yuvraj Singh
7	Windies	West Indies
8	Warnie	Shane Warne
9	Viru	Virender Sehwag
10	Tendo	Ryan ten Doeschate
11	Mushi	Mushfiqur Rahim
12	Stokesey	Ben Stokes
13	Shak	Shakib Al Hasan
14	Saqi	Saqlain Mushtaq.
15	Polly	Shaun Pollock
16	Sanga	Kumar Sangakkara

Echoism in Cricket

There are many onomatopoeia words in cricket. The researchers found 6 data classified into Echoism.

Table 07: Cricket jargons with Echoism		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Echoism
1	Boom-Boom	Imitating the sound of a bat when hitting the ball
2	Hoick	
3	Smack	
4	Spank	
5	Tonk	
6	Whack	

Boom Boom, Hoick, Smack, Spank, Tonk, Whack

All these refer to the power-hitting of a batsman. ‘Boom Boom’ is especially used as the title of the former Pakistani all-rounder Shahid Khan Afridi. ‘Hoick’ refers to slogging on the legside. ‘Smack’, ‘spank’, ‘tonk’, ‘whack’ are all used alternatively. Since all these are sound-imitating expressions, they are undoubtedly examples of echoism.

Nick

This refers to a “faint edge off the bat” made by the batters while playing a shot (Williamson, 2021).

Affixation in Cricket

The following exemplifies and explains some of the affixations in cricket. The researchers found 11 data classified into Affixation.

Table 08: Cricket jargon with Affixation		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Affixation
1	Batter	Bat (root word) + er (suffix)
2	Bowler	Bowl (root word) + er (suffix)

3	Choker	Choke (root word) + r (suffix)
4	Ducker	Duck (root word) + er (suffix)
5	Fixer	Fix (root word) + er (suffix)
6	Tailender	tail (free morpheme) + end (free morpheme / root word) + er (suffix)
7	Cutter	Cut (root word) + er (suffix)
8	Chopper	Chop (root word) + er (suffix)
9	Right/left hander	hand (root word) + er (suffix)
10	Pacer	Pace (root word) + r (suffix)
11	Spinner	Spin (root word) + er (suffix)

Acronym in Cricket

The researchers found 15 data classified into Acronyms.

Table 09: Cricket jargon with Acronym		
No.	Cricket Terminologies	Acronyms
1	ACB	Afghanistan Cricket Board
2	T20	Twenty Twenty
3	BCB	Bangladesh Cricket Board
4	PSL	Pakistan Super League
5	ODI	One Day International
6	BCCI	Board of Control for Cricket in India
7	ICC	International Cricket Council
8	BBL	Big Bash League
9	IPL	Indian Premier League
10	ICL	International Cricket League
11	BPL	Bangladesh Premier League

12	LBW	Leg Before Wicket
13	MCC	Marylebone Cricket Club
14	ECB	England and Wales Cricket Board
15	NRR	Net Run Rate

Neologism

There are some terms in cricket that fall under the criteria of neologism where the dictionary meaning has been modified or changed to adopt a new meaning which has been used as cricket terminologies. The authors gathered the following data to analyze the dictionary meaning of the words and their new meanings as neologisms:

Table 09: Cricket jargons with Neologism			
No.	Data	Dictionary Meaning	Usage in Cricket
1	Bunny	An animal	A batsman with little or no skill
2	wicket	A small door	The stumps placed on both sides of the pitch / sometimes the pitch itself
3	ton	A unit of measurement	The score of 100 made by a batsman
4	Pudding	A dessert	A slow pitch
5	Jaffa	A type of seedless sweet orange	An unplayable bowling delivery
6	googly	Unfocused	A variation of leg-spin
7	Gardening	An activity of tending to a piece of land	Batsman's repairing the unevenness of the pitch
8	Featherbed	A comfortable place to sleep	An easy scoring pitch
9	duck	A bird	Batsman's getting out without scoring or the act of bending

10	bye	Word to bid farewell	A run taken by a batter without hitting the ball with the bat or any part of his/her body
11	dolly	A play item	An easy catch
12	Lollipop	A sweet treat for children	A very easy delivery to score runs
13	Maiden	A young girl	An over costing no runs
14	Plumb	A heavy object	A straightforward LBW decision
15	Loop	a shape produced by a curve that bends round and crosses itself	The flight of the ball
16	Pair	A set of two things	A batter's getting out without scoring in a successive two innings
17	Blob	A drop of thick liquid	A score of zero / synonymous to duck
18	bouncer	A person in charge of security in a club	A bowling delivery when the bowler drops the ball short, and it goes passed the shoulder or higher part of the body of the batter

Conclusion

By summarizing the result and discussion, the authors reached a conclusion that the word formation process in Cricket terminology principally occurred in 10 types. A total of 117 data has been collected from ESPNcrickinfo.com and the authors found that compounding dominates the word formation process in cricket terms with 47 words. The other processes include, Rhyming Compound, Blending, Clipping, Borrowing, Eponym, Hypocorism, Echoism, Affixation, and Acronym. Another major type found in forming terminologies is neologism. A total of 18 data has been found under this type. As neologism does not directly fall into the word formation process, the authors decided to keep it in a separate part from the major types. Neologisms are those words which are entirely new in form or an existing word with a different meaning from the dictionary

meaning. These words are used in everyday language but in cricket jargon, they take entirely different meanings. This research is limited only to cricket jargon, its formation, historical background, and usual usage in cricket. It does not elaborate on the etymological meaning of the words. The research aimed at building of a corpus for cricket jargon while explaining the morphological analysis of the words.

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